

ABSTRACT

Geophysical electromagnetic (EM) methods have become essential tools for the exploration and monitoring of geothermal resources. The application of EM methods is primarily based on their sensitivity to the electrical conductivity of subsurface materials. Geothermal resources are usually associated with highly conductive anomalies correlated with geothermal fluids, mostly brine, due to the high dissolved salt concentration. The conductivity is further increased due to increasing temperature in the geothermal system. Exploiting this fact, the natural source EM or magnetotelluric (MT) method has traditionally been used for geothermal resource exploration and monitoring. The method is well suited for imaging deep conductivity structures. However, MT results can exhibit poor resolution due to a poor signal-to-noise ratio. On the other hand, controlled-source EM (CSEM) method, by using an artificial source, can easily improve the signal-to-noise ratio and provide higher resolution imaging with depth. We present a feasibility study of employing MT and CSEM methods for sedimentary-hosted geothermal resource exploration at Steptoe Valley in Nevada, USA. We build a 3D conductivity model of Steptoe Valley from available geological and geophysical information. The feasibility study is then performed using a massively parallel 3D CSEM/MT modeling and inversion code. The modeling is based on solving Maxwell's equations using an edge finite-element method, and the inversion employs a Gauss-Newton optimization scheme. Finally, we compare the efficiency of MT and CSEM methods for characterizing the geothermal resource at target depths of 2–3 km at Steptoe Valley.

CSEM/MT FORWARD AND INVERSE MODELING

Forward modeling: $\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E}_s - i\omega\mu\sigma \mathbf{E}_s = i\omega\mu\Delta\sigma \mathbf{E}_p$

\mathbf{E}_p : primary E-field; \mathbf{E}_s : secondary E-field; ω : frequency; and σ : conductivity

Edge finite-element solution of the PDE on tetrahedral mesh leads to:

$$\mathbf{M}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{s} \quad \mathbf{M}: \text{system matrix}; \mathbf{x}: \text{unknown fields}; \text{and } \mathbf{s}: \text{source vector}$$

$$\text{Inversion cost function: } \phi = \phi_d + \beta\phi_m \quad m = \log \sigma$$

$$\text{Data misfit: } \phi_d = \|\mathbf{W}_d\{\mathbf{d}_{\text{obs}} - \mathbf{d}_{\text{syn}}(\mathbf{m})\}\| \quad \begin{matrix} \mathbf{d}_{\text{obs}}: \text{observed data} \\ \mathbf{d}_{\text{syn}}: \text{simulated data} \end{matrix}$$

$$\text{Model misfit: } \phi_m = \|\mathbf{W}_m\{\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{m}_{\text{ref}}\}\| \quad \mathbf{W}: \text{data/model weight}$$

Gauss-Newton optimization is used to minimize the cost function [see Jaysaval et al. (2021) for details]

RESULTS

- Steptoe Valley model (Fig. 1) was built using available geological and geophysical data (Hinz et al. 2020)
- Synthetic data were then computed using 22 CSEM transmitters and 77 CSEM/MT receivers (left figure shows CSEM/MT survey layout)
- CSEM/MT data were finally inverted using the Gauss-Newton inversion approach
- Inversion results are shown in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively, for MT and CSEM data

Fig 1. Steptoe Valley resistivity model: Vertical (left) and Horizontal (right) cross-sections.

Fig 2. MT inversion result: Vertical (left) and Horizontal (right) cross-sections.

Fig 3. CSEM inversion result: Vertical (left) and Horizontal (right) cross-sections.

CSEM/MT survey layout

CONCLUSIONS

3D synthetic inversion study was performed to examine the efficiency of MT and CSEM methods to characterize the geothermal resource at Steptoe Valley. Following conclusions can be drawn from the study:

- MT inversion recovered most of the resistivity structures of the Steptoe Valley model: e.g., it recovered the top resistive layer, intermediate conductive layer, and highly-resistive basement
- However, MT didn't work well in recovering the highly-conductive geothermal reservoir and in resolving correct depth/thickness of the layers
- CSEM inversion, on the other hand, provided better resolution and depth/thickness in recovering resistivity structures as well as resolving the highly-conductive geothermal reservoir
- For deep layer, e.g., at depths > 6 km, the inverted resistivity using MT data agrees well with the true Steptoe Valley model as compared to using CSEM data

Our next step is to acquire MT and CSEM data at Steptoe Valley with a receiver grid spacing of about 2 km and transmitter spacing (for CSEM) of also about 2 km located on the east and west sides of the valley, similar to the synthetic study presented here.

REFERENCES

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